

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Fast Dissolving Tablet of Diltiazem by using Natural & Synthetic Superdisintegrants

Prince Chauhan*, Deepak Saini, Chitra Gupta

Smt. Tarawati Institute of Bio-Medical & Allied Sciences, Roorkee, Uttarakhand 247667

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 25 Jun 2026

Keywords:

Diltiazem ,
Superdisintegrants, Fast
Dissolving Tablets, Drug
release, Formulation, and
Evaluation.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20848210

ABSTRACT

Introduction : Fast dissolving tablets dissolves and split very fast in our mouth in a very less time and it does not need any liquid for consumption. The Fast dissolving tablet splits very fast into the saliva of our mouth and gives the pharmacological action of the API. **Objective :** The main objective of this study was to use a natural and synthetic super disintegrants for formulation of the fast dissolving table of Diltiazem with low substitute hydroxypropyl of cellulose (synthetic super disintegrants) and chia seed mucilage (natural superdisintegrants) as a superdisintegrants. Identification test of Diltiazem, tablet manufacturing, disintegration and dissolution time assessment, physical and chemical property and drug release assessment. **Method :** Using the Direct Compression technique The mix of all formulations was found to be satisfactory after being evaluated for several precompression parameters, including as Hausner's ratio, bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, and angle of repose. The tablets were evaluated for a number of attributes, such as weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, wetting time, water absorption ratio, disintegration time, content homogeneity, and in vitro drug release. **Result:** The four API formulations in the study, designated F1, F2, F3, and F4, were created utilizing various super disintegration agents. low substitute hydroxypropyl of cellulose 6% in F1 and 9% in F2, Salvia hispanica L. 6 % in F3 and 9% in F4 . Among F1 (97.98%), F3 (96.86%), and F4 (96.46%), F2 demonstrated 98.66% drug release at 30 minutes .The hardness of the tablet varied from 2.6 to 3.4 kg/cm², Thickness is 2.22 to 2.26 mm and friability is 0.48 to 0.62% according to the results. **Conclusion:** The goal of the study was to create Fast dissolving tablets for Diltiazem using natural and synthetic polymers, such as low substitute hydroxypropyl of cellulose or Salvia hispanica L., to enhance the API's drug release.

INTRODUCTION

Fast dissolving tablet

Fast dissolving tablets dissolves and split very fast in our mouth in a very less time and it does not

***Corresponding Author:** Prince Chauhan

Address: Smt. Tarawati Institute of Bio-Medical & Allied Sciences, Roorkee, Uttarakhand 247667

Email ✉ : oohimanshusharma944@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

need any liquid for consumption. The Fast dissolving tablet splits very fast into the saliva of our mouth and gives the pharmacological action of the API. In comparison with normal tablets, oral dispersible Tablet have good compliance with patients, improved drug plasma concentration

We use oral route over other routes of administration because of easy administration of dosage form, no pain during administration and nil patient non-compliance. Tablets and capsules are the most widely used dosage form. But one of the major disadvantages of tablet dosage forms is that they are tough to swallow. To overcome this type of hurdle in swallowing, Formulation department has developed a system which is fast dissolving i.e. Fast dissolving tablet

They offer advantages over swallowed tablet. To swallow the tablet is very tough especially for small children and old age patients. The different methods that are being used for the formulation of FDT are lyophilization, blow drying, molding, sublimation and direct compression.[1,2]

Need of fast dissolving drug delivery system

The oral route is the most popular because of ease of ingestion, avoidance of pain, versatility to accommodate different types of drug candidates and most importantly, patient compliance. In addition, solid oral delivery systems do not require sterile conditions and are therefore less costly to manufacture. Many pharmaceutical dosages are taken by mouth as pills, such as tablets and capsules. Recently, many novel technologies for oral delivery have become available to address the physicochemical and pharmacokinetic characteristics of drugs and to improve patient compliance.[3]

All age groups frequently have dysphagia, or difficulty swallowing. found that approximately

35% of the general population, 30–40% of elderly institutionalized patients, and 8–22% of all individuals in long-term care facilities have dysphagia. Tablet size, surface, form, and taste are the most frequently complained about aspects of tablet swallowing problems.

Among all the dosage forms that are currently accessible, tablets are the most commonly utilized due to their ease of administration, affordability, and elegance. Tablets are oral, single-dose preparations meant for administration. Among the excipients utilized in the tablet manufacturing process are lubricants, disintegrants, binder, glidants, etc. Certain tablets are chewed or consumed whole, while others dissolve or disperse in water before delivery, and yet others are placed in the mouth to release the active ingredient. Oral administration is the most common route of drug delivery, with advantages including high patient compliance, low risk of infection and minimal sterility constraints, which simplifies the production process and reduces costs.

Worldwide, hypertension is a major cause of disease and mortality. It is one of the leading causes of chronic renal disease, overall mortality rates, and cardiovascular issues such as ischemic heart disease, stroke, and heart failure. As the population ages, it is expected that the number of people with hypertension would increase. Resistant hypertension affects between 10% and 15% of people undergoing hypertension medication.[4,5]

In the absence of confirmatory testing, resistant hypertension is defined as blood pressure readings that stay above the target even when the patient takes three or more antihypertensive drugs—typically a diuretic—or requires four or more drugs to effectively control blood pressure.

Improving treatments for resistant hypertension is crucial since multiple studies show that people with this illness are more likely to have negative consequences. Heart attacks, ischemic heart disease, heart failure, strokes, Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) or end-stage renal disease, and mortality were almost twice as common among patients with resistant hypertension in large retrospective studies with 200,000–400,000 participants.

Additionally, patients with particular comorbidities, such as CKD, ischemic heart disease, obesity, diabetes, and obstructive sleep apnea, have worse results when they have resistant hypertension.[6,7]

Diltiazem hydrochloride

Diltiazem is a calcium channel blocker that blocks calcium channels in the heart and blood vessels. By relaxing the blood arteries, reducing blood pressure, and boosting the heart's blood and oxygen flow, this decreases the strain on the heart.

Figure: 1 Diltiazem

Diltiazem has the longest half-life, lasting between 30 and 50 hours. This extended half-life makes it possible to take the medication once daily, which is beneficial. The FDA first approved amlodipine in 1987, and it is currently sold under the brand name Diltiazem. Diltiazem a calcium antagonist

dihydropyridine, inhibits the entrance of calcium ions into cardiac and vascular smooth muscle. Diltiazem is used to treat hypertension in both young and elderly people. When an instant release formulation is taken orally, it takes six to eight hours for the therapeutic action to manifest.[8,9]

Diltiazem bind on the L-shape calcium binding site and stop the intake of calcium ion in smooth muscle. Dihydropyridine more potent action on blood vessels than heart muscle and prevent hypertension. Non-dihydropyridine more potent action on heart muscle then blood vessels and treat hypertension. Diltiazem is use also alone and combination with other medicine such as hydrochlorothiazide to treat HTN.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Diltiazem hydrochloride is given as gift sample by Acme generics Pharma from Baddi microcrystalline cellulose Acme generics Pharma from Baddi. Natural Superdisintegrants by Local market, Talc and magnesium stearate were Acme generics Pharma from Baddi.

Extraction

Salvia hispanica

Salvia Hispanic seeds were steeped in water for a whole night (the seed-solvent ratio was 1:20), mixed on a magnetic stirrer for an hour, and then heated for 30 minutes to completely release the mucilage into the water. Centrifuging the liquid for 50 minutes at 5000 rpm produced three separate layers. Dry the gel layer at 50°C in a hot air oven. The product was stored at room temperature in desiccators for subsequent use after being powdered and passing through sieve no. 80.[10]

Figure: 2 Salvia Hiaspanica

Table:1 Evaluation of Salvia hispanica

Sr. No	Consistent	Name of test	Observation	Result
1	Molisch's test	Carbohydrate Test	Violet or purple ring confirms	+ve
2	Mayer's reagent	Alkaloid Test	opalescence or yellowish precipitate	-ve
3	Ferric chloride	Tannins Test	blackish blue color precipitate	-ve
4	Keller-Kilani test	Glycosides Test	formed Reddish brown layer	+ve
5	Ninhydrin Test	Protein Test	Appearance blue colour	-ve

Table 2: Composition of Experimental Batches of Tablets

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
Diltiazem	60	60	60	60
low substitute hydroxypropyl of cellulose	6	9	-	-
Salvia Hispanic	-	-	6	9
Mannitol	50	50	50	50
Microcrystalline cellulose	20	20	20	20
Aspartame	10	10	10	10
Magnesium stearate	34	31	34	31
Talc	20	20	21	21
Total	200	200	200	200

Precompression study

Determination of melting point determining the melting point The medication Diltiazem is to be placed into a fused capillary tube with one end and placed within a digital melting point instrument (Perfit India, Model No. REC2802582). The melting point of a medicine is the temperature at which it begins to melt.[11]

Determination of λ max of Diltiazem Using a UV-visible spectrometer (UV-2450, Shimadzu), the UV spectra of Diltiazem was produced. The medication was introduced to a 100 ml volumetric

flask with an accurate weight of 10 mg. Using 100 μ g/ml of water, the volume was increased to 100 ml. This was a stock solution that was applied. This solution (100 μ g/ml) was used to generate appropriate working solutions at various concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 μ g/ml). After scanning the resulting solution from 400 to 200 nm, the maximum wavelength in each of the solvents was determined by recording the spectra. A spectrophotometer was used to measure each standard solution's absorbance. [12,13]

Bulk density powder's bulk density varies with powder consolidation and is influenced by particle packing. The bulk powder was poured into a graduated cylinder using a large funnel, and the weight and volume were measured to determine the apparent bulk density. The formula for calculating bulk density is as follows:.[14]

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \frac{\text{Weight of powder}}{\text{Bulk Volume}}$$

Angle of repose (θ) The maximum angle that can exist between a powder pile's surface and a horizontal plane is known as the angle of repose.

By measuring the angle of repose, one can determine the frictional force in loose powder or grains[14]

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} h/r$$

Hausner's ratio One measure of powder flow easiness that is not direct is Hausner's ratio Here's the formula that calculates it: [15,16]

$$H = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

Compressibility Index (Carr's Index) Carr's devised a second indirect technique for determining powder flow from bulk densities. Powder arch or bridge strength and stability can be directly determined by calculating the % compressibility of the powder. Equation following is used to compute it.[17,18]

Compressibility Index =

$$100 \times \frac{(\text{Tapped Density} - \text{Bulk Density})}{\text{Tapped density}}$$

POST COMPRESSION STUDIES

Weight variation test: Twenty tablets of the formulation type were weighed individually using an electronic scale, the average weight was determined, and the weights of each tablet were compared to the average to find weight differences. [19,20]

%weight variation =

$$\frac{\text{Individual weight} - \text{average weight}}{\text{individual weight}} \times 100$$

Thickness and diameter Physical dimensions are the regulated parameter used in formulation preparation. In the marketplace and for regularity of tablet formulations, thickness and diameter are important factors. measurements were verified in

millimeters using a "Digital vernier caliper." The thickness of the tablets was measured using a Vernier calipers. Average values were calculated using thirty of the formulation's pills.[21,22,23]

Hardness Before being utilized, a tablet's hardness dictates how resilient it is to shipping, handling, storage, and transit conditions. Six tablets per formulation were tested for hardness using the Monsanto hardness tester. The tablet was held along its oblong axis between the tester's two jaws. Right now, the reading should be 0 kg/cm². [24,25]

Friability Friability is a measure of tablet strength. The following procedure was used to assess friability using a Roche Friabilator: In this test, tablets are subjected to the combined effects of impact abrasion by being dropped from a distance of six inches with each rotation of a plastic container rotating at a speed of 25 rpm. [26,27]

%FRIABILITY =

$$\frac{\text{INITIAL WEIGHT} - \text{FINAL WEIGHT}}{\text{INITIAL WEIGHT}} \times 100$$

Disintegration test A USP disintegration device utilizing phosphate buffer at pH 6.8 was used to measure time it took for mouth-dispersing pills to dissolve. medium had a capacity of 900 milliliters and a temperature of 37 °C±2 °C. amount of time (measured in seconds) required for tablet to completely dissolve and leave no discernible mass on the mesh was recorded. [28,29]

In vitro dissolution test The USP type II (paddle) instrument was used to study how the medication was released from the tablet. In this method, 900 milliliters of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer served as the dissolve media, and the paddle was rotated at a steady 500 revolutions per minute. The medium's temperature was kept at 37°C±0.5 °C. For seven

minutes, a five-milliliter sample was taken out one minute at a time.[30,31]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Finding the melting point The drug Diltiazem will be put into a one-end fused capillary tube and kept in a digital melting point device. The melting point of drug is $166 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Calibration Curve of Diltiazem In 6.8 pH Phosphate Buffer Solution at 236 λ max

Method is the standard plot of Diltiazem in Solution of 6.8 pH Phosphate Buffer, as explained in section shows that the Diltiazem standard curve

complied with Beer's law. The R2 value and linearity between 1-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were determined to be at nm 0.9987, 239 nm 0.9981, and 236 nm 0.9986.

Table: 3 calibration curve data of diltiazem

Conc. of Drug in Phosphate Buffer Sulation ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	λ max 236
3	0.085 ± 0.036
6	0.185 ± 0.066
9	0.365 ± 0.034
12	0.458 ± 0.012
15	0.632 ± 0.015
18	0.762 ± 0.0048
21	0.826 ± 0.042
24	0.954 ± 0.046

Figure:3 calibration cure of Diltiazem

Table: 4 Precompression parameters for fast dissolving tablets of F1 to F4 Formulation code

Formulation	Angle of repose (g/ml)	Bulk density	Tapped density (g/ml)	Compressibility index (%)	Hausner's ratio
F1	27.41 ± 0.014	0.345 ± 0.0036	0.430 ± 0.0048	14.16 ± 1.14	1.058
F2	26.42 ± 0.017	0.353 ± 0.0034	0.422 ± 0.0054	13.18 ± 1.56	1.136
F3	28.12 ± 0.018	0.372 ± 0.0056	0.388 ± 0.0044	16.16 ± 2.56	1.204
F4	30.46 ± 0.026	0.376 ± 0.0046	0.412 ± 0.0058	15.24 ± 2.22	1.126

Table:5 Precompression parameters for fast dissolving tablets of F1 to F4 Formulation code

Formulation code	Thickness (mm) (mean \pm SD)	Hardness at* Kg/cm2 +-S-D	Friability Percentage	Time in secs +-S.D	(F1) Wt. mgs
F1	2.22 ± 0.012	3.32 ± 0.022	$0.51 \pm 0.04\%$	32 ± 1.56	198 ± 0.12
F2	2.26 ± 0.008	3.42 ± 0.136	$0.48 \pm 0.02\%$	24 ± 1.26	196 ± 0.04
F3	2.24 ± 0.024	3.48 ± 0.036	$0.62 \pm 0.04\%$	42 ± 1.24	204 ± 0.16
F4	2.26 ± 0.012	2.66 ± 0.025	$0.56 \pm 0.05\%$	38 ± 1.66	198 ± 0.08

Table:6 Drug releasing of Diltiazem

Time	%Drug Release (F1)	%Drug Release (F2)	%Drug Release (F3)	%Drug Release (F4)
0	0	0	0	0
5	74.26	76.44	74.48	68.56
10	80.22	79.92	79.54	71.46
15	92.21	86.45	82.23	85.56
20	93.12	92.40	84.86	89.86
25	97.26	96.68	89.72	92.65
30	97.98	98.66	96.86	96.46

Figure:4 Drug releasing of Diltiazem

Figure:5 Drug releasing of Diltiazem

Figure:6 Drug releasing of Diltiazem

Figure:7 Drug releasing of Diltiazem

CONCLUSION

The four API formulations in the study, F1, F2, F3, and F4, were created utilizing various super disintegration agents. Low replacement hydroxypropyl of cellulose: 6% in F1 and 9% in F2; mucilage from chai seeds: 6% in F3 and 9% in F4. Among F1 (97.98%), F3 (96.86%), and F4 (96.46%), F2 demonstrated 98.66% drug release at 30 minutes in the research. The hardness of the tabs varied from 2.6 to 3.4 kg/cm², Thickness is 2.22 to 2.26 mm and friability is 0.48 to 0.62% according to the results. The tablet's formulation may lead to a rise in patient complaints and medical issues. However, research is required to determine the disintegration agent's ideal concentration and stability. The study's use of super disintegrating agents improved the API mod peen's drug release, leading to a notable and possible improvement in therapeutic effects.

REFERENCES

1. Kuczyńska J, Nieradko-Iwanicka B. The effect of ketoprofen lysine salt on mucosa of rat stomach after ethyl alcohol intoxication. *Biomed Pharmacother.* 2021;141:111938.
2. Cheng YT, Lin JA, Jhang JJ, Yen GC. Protocatechuic acid-mediated DJ-1/PARK7 activation followed by PI3K/mTOR signaling pathway activation as a novel mechanism for protection against ketoprofen-induced oxidative damage in the gastrointestinal mucosa. *Free Radic Biol Med.* 2019;130:35-47.
3. Tejvir Kaur., Bhawandeep Gill., Sandeep Kumar., Gupta G D., "Mouth Dissolving Tablets". *Int J.Cur Pharm Res.* 2011;3(1):1-7.
4. Ujjwal Nautiyal., Satinderjeet Singh., Ramandeep Singh., Gopal., Satinder Kakar., "Fast Dissolving Tablets as a Novel Boon". *J. Pharm. Chem. Bio. Sci.* 2014;2(1):5-26.
5. Alok Kumar Gupta., Anuj Mittal., Jha K K. "Fast Dissolving Tablets". *J.Pharm.* 2012;1(1):1-8.
6. Dipan Roy, Anjan De, Souvik Biswas, Nabanita Pramanick, Arijit Das, Sriparna Mondal, Fast dissolving tablets: Past, present and future, *Indian Drugs*, 2010;47(6):5-11.
7. Arunachalam A., Karthikeyan M., AshutoshKumar., Kishore Konam., Potabathula hari Prasad., Sethuraman S., Manidipa S. "Fast Dissolving Drug Delivery System". *J. Glo Tre Pharm Sci.* 2010;1(1):92-110.
8. Ved Parkash, Saurabh Maan, Deepika, Shiv Kumar Yadav², Hemlata, Vikas Jogpal, Fast disintegrating tablets: Opportunity in drug delivery system, *JAPTR*, 2011;2(4):223-235.
9. Ashish P., Harsoliya M S., Pathan M K., Shruti S., "Formulation of Mouth Dissolving Tablet". *Int. J. Pharm. Cli. Sci.* 2011;3(5),1-8.

10. Nehal Siddiqui Md., Garima Garg., Pramod Kumar Sharma., "Fast Dissolving Tablets". *Int.J.Pharm. Sci.* 2010;4(2):87-96.
11. Deshmukh Keshav Ram., Patel Vidyanand., Verma Shekhar., Pandey Alok Kumar., Dewangan Pramod., 2011. "A Mouth Dissolving Tablet Technique". *Int J. Res Ayur Pharm.* 2011;2(1): 66-74.
12. Ashish et al, Mouth Dissolving Tablets: A Review, *Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics*; 2013, 3(2), 207-214
13. Bandari S, Mittapalli RK, Gannu R and Rao YM. Orodispersible Tablets: An overview, *Asian J. Pharm.* 2008; 2: 2-11.
14. Garje VN, Gaikwad DD Jadhav SL and Gadhav MV. Mouth Dissolving tablets, a novel approach in tableting. *Int. J. Univers. Pharm. Life Sci.* 2012; 2: 336-347.
15. Reddy LH, Ghosh B and Rajneesh. Fast dissolving drug delivery System: A review on literature. *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.* 2002; 64: 331-336.
16. Pahwa R, Piplani M, Sharma PC, Kaushik D, Nanda S, Orally Disintegrating Tablets – Friendly to Pediatrics and Geriatrics. *Archives of Applied Science Research*, 2010; 2(2): 35-48
17. Divate S, Kavitha K, Sockan GN, Fast disintegrating Tablets- An emerging trend. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 2011; 6(2): 18-22.
18. Panigrahi R, Behera S. A Review on fast dissolving Tablets. *Webmed Central Quality and patient safety*, 2010; 1(9): WMC00809.
19. Bhowmik D, Chiranjib B, Krishnakanth, Pankaj, Chandira MR, Fast Dissolving Tablet: An Overview, *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2009; 1(1): 163-177.
20. Mishra B, Shukla D, Chakraborty S, Singh S, Mouth Dissolving Tablets I: An Overview of Formulation Technology, *Scientia Pharmaceutica*, 2009; 77: 309–326.
21. Shaikh S, Khirsagar R.V, Quazi A. Fast Disintegrating Tablets: An Overview Of Formulation And Technology. *Inter J. Pharmacy Pharma Sci*, 2010; 2(3): 9-15.
22. Habib W, Khankari R, Hontz J. Fast-dissolve drug delivery system. *Crit Rev Ther Drug Carrier Syst* 2000; 17: 61-72.
23. Rubinstein, MH., 2000 Tablets In: "Aulton", ME(Ed.), *Pharmaceutics, The Science Of Dosage Form Design* Churchill Livingstone, Edinburgh London Melbourne and New York, page 305
24. Bhupathi S.K, Jithendra R, Bandaru and Bhupathi V. V. Design and evaluation of fast dissolving tablet Of Terbutaline Sulphate. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical*, 2012;138-153.
25. Shrivastava M, Chourasiya D, Soni S, Patidar D, Jatav R. Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of Mouth dissolving tablets of phenytoin sodium using Different disintegrating agent. *IJNDDT*, 2012; 249-255.
26. Reddy LH, Ghosh B, Rajneesh. Fast dissolving drug delivery systems: A review of the literature. *Indian J Pharm Sci* 2002 Jul; 64(4): 331-6.
27. Kumari S, Visht S, Sharma PK, Yadav RK. Fast Dissolving Drug Delivery System: Review Article. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*. 2010; 3(6): 1444- 1449.
28. Kumar V. Dinesh, Sharma Ira, Sharma Vipin, A comprehensive review on fast dissolving tablet technology, *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science* 01 (05), 2011,50-58.
29. *International Journal of Pharm Tech Research CODEN (USA): IJPRIF ISSN: 0974-4304 Vol.1, No.4, pp 10791091, Oct-Dec 2009.*
30. 11. Hamilton EL, Luts EM. Advanced Orally disintegrating tablets bring significant

benefits to patients and product life cycle,
Drug Deliv Technol, 5(1), 2005, 3437.

31. D. Shukla et al., Mouth Dissolving Tablets I: An Overview of Formulation Technology, Scientia Pharmaceutica. 2009; 76; 309326.

HOW TO CITE: Prince Chauhan, Deepak Saini, Chitra Gupta, Formulation and Evaluation of Fast Dissolving Tablet of Diltiazem by using Natural & Synthetic Superdisintegrants, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2026, Vol 4, Issue 6, 6503-6512.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20848210>

